

1 **Title**

2 Without words: the effects of packaging imagery on consumer perception and response

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13 **Abstract**

14 Scientific interest in understanding how packaging imagery influence consumer perception and
15 response has increased in the last decade. Research show that the attributes of what is depicted on
16 imagery anchor consumers' judgements, affecting how the product within is evaluated and perceived,
17 and that consumers interpret the symbolic attributes of imagery according to their grounded bodily
18 experience with the physical world. In addition, recent advances show that the meaning inferred from
19 ambiguous images can be modulated by manipulating some of the images' features, and that
20 imagery can play a relevant role in terms of modulating consumption and promoting health choices.
21 The practical implications of these findings are discussed.

22 **Keywords**

23 Packaging design; Semiotic; Embodiment; Health promotion

24 **Highlights**

- 25 • Literature on the effects of packaging imagery on consumer perception is summarized.
26 • Consumers infer meaning from packaging imagery, thus shaping their expectations.
27 • The salient attributes of the imagery tend to be projected to the packaged product.
28 • Packaging imagery can be used to nudge consumers to healthy food choices.
29 • Despite its advantages, using packaging imagery is not always recommended.

1 **1. Introduction**

2 In the shopping context, where consumers decide which food products to buy by spending a limited
3 amount of time and cognitive resources [1], packaging helps consumers decide which product to
4 choose by capturing their attention and convincing them that it contains the product which best suits
5 their needs. Thus, its role in the different phases of the consumption process has attracted a growing
6 scientific interest [2,3]. Packaging cues such as imagery, colour, weight, or even how the package
7 sounds can exert an influence on consumer perception, not only at the buying stage (i.e., when
8 expectations are usually set) but also on the overall consumption experience [4].

9 The specific case of packaging imagery has not been as extensively studied as other packaging cues
10 such as colour [5], despite being also a prominent packaging cue. However, research conducted in
11 the last decade, and specially in recent years, suggest that each of the different features of the
12 images depicted on food packaging has the ability both to convey meaning and to affect consumer
13 perception and consumer behaviour (see Table 1 for a summary of the literature on packaging
14 imagery conducted in the last years). This paper aims to summarize the latest findings in this topic,
15 putting a special emphasis on how imagery can be used to promote healthy eating and offering a
16 series of practical tips regarding when it is recommended (or not) to use packaging imagery.

17 **2. Imagery as a relevant packaging visual cue and a semantic visual sign**

18 One may wonder what would be the point in paying attention to an apparently trivial cue such as
19 imagery, given that texts and verbal claims are always present in a packaging. If textual information
20 is provided, wouldn't that be enough to effectively convey information to consumers? Research
21 conducted almost two decades ago suggests that it is not as straightforward as it seems, since
22 imagery may shape expectations about the product attributes even when concrete textual information
23 is provided [6]. The reason why that may happen is twofold. On the one hand, the images depicted
24 on packaging are usually salient cues which quickly attract consumer attention [7,8], and which
25 consumers consciously (and unconsciously) use to infer product information [9,10]. And on the other
26 hand, images are more vivid and their processing requires less cognitive effort, so they have been
27 suggested to generate expectations more quickly than texts [11]. Given that the first impression of a
28 stimulus tends to affect its subsequent evaluation [12], it is understandable that the information
29 transmitted by imagery may outweigh or compete with the information transmitted by the textual
30 claims. Considering the key role of congruence between the different packaging cues when it comes
31 to convey product information [13,14], it is relevant for both designers and practitioners to understand
32 the processes and mechanisms by which this interpretation process takes place in order to avoid
33 situations in which the meaning given to the imagery does not match that of other packaging cues
34 (such as that of textual claims).

35 However, an image by itself is ambiguous and can evoke many interpretations in the mind of the
36 consumer (e.g., the image of a strawberry depicted on a yoghurt package can be interpreted as
37 meaning that the yoghurt is made with strawberries, has strawberries on it, has strawberry flavour,
38 and so on). This property of imagery is known as propositional (syntactic) indeterminacy, and is
39 responsible for the communication through images to be considered "weak" —since the receptor can
40 never be sure what the sender had in mind or the way in which the stimulus should be interpreted

1 [11]. Indeed, this is the main reason why designers find it so hard to anticipate the meaning that
2 consumers will infer from a given image: they must understand and untangle the codes and language
3 used by consumers in order to posit the desired message as unambiguously as possible, since
4 confusion or misunderstanding could lead to setting erroneous expectations [15,16].

5 Recently, some efforts have been made seeking to better understand how ambiguous images are
6 interpreted in the context of food packaging. A recent study demonstrated that consumers tend to
7 interpret a potentially ambiguous image by relying on the congruence of any of its possible meanings
8 with the possible attributes of the product with which it is displayed, thus highlighting the key role of
9 congruency in the interpretation process [14]. Trying to go a step further, the same team conducted
10 another study in which they investigated how a specific meaning is chosen when several congruent
11 meanings are available. Building on cross-modal correspondence literature, they proposed and
12 demonstrated that the image's features (namely, its angularity) can be used to convey product
13 information and thus modulate consumer interpretation, thereby affecting expectations (Figure 1)
14 [17].

15 **3. The effects of manipulating what is depicted on the image**

16 One of the most prominent features of packaging imagery is what is depicted in it (i.e., its subject), so
17 most of the studies conducted so far have focused on analysing the consequences of its
18 manipulation. Overall, images can be classified as those that show food imagery and those that show
19 other subjects. This distinction is useful due to the fact that food images are salient stimuli that
20 quickly and involuntarily attract consumer attention and increase salivation and appetite, and thereby
21 may enhance willingness to buy [18]. Indeed, some studies suggest that consumers increasingly
22 demand to see the product before opening the package, which is possible through images or
23 transparent materials (so the impact of transparent windows has begun to attract a scientific interest
24 [18,19]).

25 **3.1. Food imagery**

26 Regarding food imagery, it is worth noting that depicted subjects vary. The most common case is to
27 show the product contained inside the package and/or the ingredients or food products that give it its
28 aroma/flavour, but it is not uncommon to see packages in which food products not included within are
29 depicted accompanying the main product in the form of a serving suggestion. Since Underwood and
30 Klein conducted one of the first studies which analysed the effect of packaging images on consumer
31 judgements and beliefs towards the product [20], a modest but growing number of studies have
32 demonstrated that depicting food products on the packaging elicits sensory associations related to
33 texture, appearance, and taste [21–23], and that consumers seem to project the attributes of the
34 depicted products onto the main product. For example, consumers tend to estimate the calorie
35 content of the main product relying on the calorie content of the garnish depicted on the serving
36 suggestion [24–26], or to expect a soft cheese to be sweeter if it is shown in the package together
37 with a quince instead of together with a salad, despite the fact that none of those products is directly
38 related to the cheese itself nor contained within the package (Figure 2) [27]. Moreover, depicting the
39 major taste-giving ingredient in the package (e.g., the fruits that give their flavour to some candy)

1 increases the quantity of natural product believed to have been used in the product elaboration (yet
2 consumers' food knowledge level moderates this effect) [11].

3 Although it should be noted that the influence of imagery is stronger on expectations than in
4 perception during tasting [28] (as it happens with other packaging cues [29]), some studies have
5 reported that in some cases it may even affect the sensory perception of the product. Thus, seeing
6 product-congruent and positive-valenced images during consumption (as opposed to seeing product-
7 incongruent or negative-valenced images) leads to higher taste evaluations and a positive attitude
8 towards the product (e.g., seeing a picture of edible oranges when drinking orange juice leads to a
9 better product evaluation than seeing a picture of spoiled inedible oranges or an unrelated image)
10 [30,31]. Moreover, the visual appearance of the apple depicted on a jar of apple sauce (i.e., whether
11 it is red or green) has been reported to affect liking, willingness to buy and some sensory attributes
12 for some cohorts of consumers. Specifically, men perceive the apple sauce from the jar depicting a
13 red apple as being slightly sweeter than the apple sauce from the jar depicting a green apple, while
14 women evaluate the apple sauce from the jar depicting a green apple as being more acidic than the
15 sauce coming from the jar displaying a red apple [32].

16 Specific features of the image's subject such as the level of processing of the product depicted on
17 the image may also affect consumer perception and response. Previous studies suggest that
18 showing the product unprocessed rather than processed (e.g., a raw orange instead of a glass of
19 orange juice) enhances healthful and naturalness perception and perceived taste pureness, thereby
20 affecting product consumption and purchase intention [33–35]. However, note that these effects
21 (which have been reported to apply specially for some subsets of consumers, such as those who are
22 health-conscious [34]) may be mitigated or even occur the other way around if the depicted
23 unprocessed product is inedible: for example, depicting a fully processed and ready to consume
24 potato crisp in a bag of crisps raises higher sensory expectations and willingness to buy than
25 depicting the product unprocessed (i.e., a raw potato) [22]. Although further research should be
26 needed to assess why this happens, a possible explanation for this apparent contradiction may be
27 that seeing raw inedible food, while it is inherently natural and unprocessed, may not trigger the
28 positive evaluations that arise when seeing raw and unprocessed edible food. In addition, other
29 subtle manipulations have also proven to be effective, such as that of the implied movement of the
30 image: showing the product moving rather than still increases perceived freshness, food acceptance,
31 and taste expectations [36,37].

32 Furthermore, consumers use the quantity of product depicted on the image as a heuristic to infer how
33 much product is contained within the package, which in turn affects how much product is consumed.
34 Research demonstrates that the number of product units shown (where the more units, the more
35 consumption [12]), the perceived size of the serving portion depicted (where the bigger the perceived
36 portion, the bigger the consumption [38–40]) or the size of the image itself (where the bigger the
37 image, the bigger the consumption [41]) all can affect quantity estimation and consumption behaviour
38 (Figure 3).

1 **3.2. Non-food imagery**

2 Regarding non-food imagery, a distinction can be made between images depicting product-related
3 and non-product-related subjects. Consider non-food-product-related subjects as those images
4 depicting themes indirectly related to the product, such as a bucolic landscape, a table setting or
5 depictions of people consuming the product. The few papers devoted to the study of these kinds of
6 imagery indicate that showing images idealising the product origins or production processes (e.g., a
7 landscape or a farm) helps to convey concepts like *authenticity* or *quality* [42–44], whereas
8 manipulating the cutlery and the elements depicted surrounding the product may help to enhance (or
9 reduce) the product salience and thus to increase attention [45]. Moreover, displaying images
10 depicting other consumers tasting and enjoying the product may increase the perceived product
11 palatability for unhealthy product categories, since the image serves as a social proof of the
12 appropriateness of such a consumption [46,47]. Specifically, the images depicting consumers about
13 to engage in eating the food (e.g., moving food to mouth or taking a bite) are more likely to enhance
14 desire and consumption [48].

15 On the other hand, non-food non-product-related subjects refer to images that apparently have
16 nothing to do with the product, but usually have a symbolic meaning and require a metaphorical
17 (rather than a literal) interpretation. Although the processing of these kind of imagery require a
18 greater cognitive effort than that needed to process literal images [14], they are capable of producing
19 higher level inferences about the product's expected attributes or outcomes [49]. Hence, caffeine
20 content of two cola drinks can be expressed by manipulating the attitude of the persons depicted on
21 the packaging [6], the depiction of health imagery (i.e., images that have a symbolic health-related
22 meaning, such as people exercising) can increase perceived healthfulness [50,51], coffee strength
23 can be enhanced if it is conveyed through a visual metaphor (e.g., the image of a lion) [28], and the
24 sensory information inferred by consumers can be modulated by manipulating an image of fire
25 depicted in the package (Figure 1) [14,17]. In addition, it is worth noting that the emotional valence of
26 the imagery may be transferred to the product [52], which in turn may affect sensory evaluations [53].

27 **4. The effects of manipulating other imagery's features**

28 Some researchers have suggested that an approach based in the embodied cognition framework
29 may help to understand some of the subtler effects that manipulating other imagery's features
30 different that the image's subject has on consumer perception and response. The embodied
31 cognition framework proposes that people interpret abstract and symbolic concepts in terms of daily
32 physical interactions, and thus postulates that the representation of such concepts is grounded in
33 direct bodily experience with the physical world. For example, according to this approach, people
34 tend to assume that an object that is placed *high* is lighter than an object that is placed *low*, since in
35 our everyday experience the heavier objects usually are placed near the ground [54,55].

36 Building in this framework, some studies have investigated the embodied associations between the
37 image's spatial location in the package and the sensory and affective evaluations made by
38 consumers, demonstrating that the image's spatial location can convey the notion of heaviness.
39 Thus, placing the image on the visually heavier locations (i.e., bottom, right, or bottom-right positions
40 of the package) triggers associations with concepts like heaviness and strength, and so enhances (or

1 diminishes) willingness to buy depending on the contextual valence of the concept of heaviness (e.g.,
2 a healthy snack is preferred to be perceived as light, so placing the image in a lighter location is
3 preferred) [28,54,56–59]. Moreover, the vertical axis of the package may also be used to convey the
4 concept of quality, with the higher locations of the label being associated with higher quality [60]. In
5 turn, other studies have suggested that the horizontal axis of the packaging may also be used to
6 convey a conceptualization of time [61], and that concepts such as *care* and *closeness* can be
7 conveyed through the composition and the layout of the imagery [62]. Even the image's orientation
8 and the camera angle in which the picture is shown have been reported to play a role in these
9 processes. Thus, depicting the spoon at the right side of a plate of soup in the package picture
10 facilitates the mental simulation of the act of consuming it and thereby enhances purchase intentions
11 [63], while an image taken with an upward camera angle (compared to a downward camera angle)
12 enhances the perception of the depicted product as being luxurious [64]. Furthermore, the orientation
13 in which the image is shown has the ability to affect evaluations, since some images' orientations are
14 preferred over others [65].

15 Conversely, the impact of manipulating the image's pictorial style (i.e., whether the image is a
16 drawing or a photograph) remains far from clear: while some researchers have found drawings to
17 enhance the expectations of some product attributes [66], and others have suggested the opposite
18 effect (i.e. the expectations being enhanced when using a photograph instead of a drawing) [67–69],
19 other authors have failed to find any of such effects [11]. Relatedly, design cuteness have been
20 shown to increase tastiness perceptions while decreasing healthfulness perceptions, thus favouring
21 unhealthy food choices [70]. Moreover, the influence of other features of the image such as its
22 brightness or its contrast remains largely to be studied, despite those factors having been proven to
23 be relevant with other cues such as colour [71,72].

24 **5. Practical implications**

25 Taken together, these findings offer interesting insights into how consumers process and interpret
26 packaging imagery. As final remarks, we highlight some practical implications of the work outlined
27 here that may be of interest to both designers and practitioners alike. Specifically, we will now outline
28 how packaging imagery can be used to nudge consumers into healthy food choices and what the
29 risks and precautions are that should be taken when working with packaging imagery.

30 **5.1. Conveying product healthfulness**

31 The steady growth of cases of people suffering from overweight and obesity due to poor dietary
32 choices has made helping consumers to choose healthy foods a priority research subject for the
33 scientific community. In this context, several studies have been conducted aiming to understand how
34 packaging cues influence food choice and consumption. For instance, the convenience of using
35 product imagery or transparent windows in terms of enhancing perceived healthfulness has been
36 discussed in previous studies [18], as well as the role of front-of-pack implicit visual cues [73]. In
37 addition, the impact and effectiveness of front-of-package nutrition labels and health warnings is
38 being intensively studied [74,75]. However, despite a recent analysis showing that designers
39 commonly rely on imagery when it comes to communicate product healthfulness [49], the role of
40 imagery in this context has received comparatively much less attention.

1 In sum, literature shows that imagery can be used to modulate the healthfulness expectations of a
2 product and to promote healthy eating mainly in three different ways. Firstly, the healthfulness of the
3 product may be highlighted by depicting imagery related to health [50,51] or sustainability [35], by
4 depicting healthy foods next to the product [24–27], or by placing the image in the upper part of the
5 package front [54,56]. Secondly, imagery may be used to make healthy products more appealing
6 (thereby increasing intention to purchase) by displaying an aesthetically pleasant picture of the
7 product [18,31], by enhancing expectations of a goal sensory attribute [17,22,27], or by helping
8 consumers to mentally simulate consumption [63] (indeed, the scientific interest in understanding the
9 role of instructed mental simulations on wanting and food choice has grown in the last years [76], and
10 its application to the study of packaging imagery may open new and interesting research lines). And
11 thirdly, in the case of indulgent products, consumption may be tempered by depicting a low number
12 of product units on the package [12], by reducing the actual (or perceived) size of the serving portion
13 [38–40], by depicting the product with a photograph rather than with an illustration [69], or by showing
14 the recommended serving portion through imagery rather than through a text [77]. In contrast, cute
15 designs [70] or the depiction of attractive faces [78] may favour the choice of indulgent products, so
16 they should be avoided when trying to promote healthy eating.

17 However, it is worth highlighting that these insights could also be used to mislead consumers by
18 making unhealthy products look more healthful and thereby favouring unhealthy product choices. It
19 is a risk that should not be overlooked, and thus these insights are also of interest to policy makers
20 who watch over consumer rights and health promotion.

21 **5.2. Cautions and good practices when using packaging imagery**

22 Some hints and good practices may be outlined from the research conducted in the last years when
23 it comes to deciding whether to use packaging imagery. Research show that it matters what is
24 depicted on the image (and how), since a poor image choice can have a more negative effect on
25 consumer expectations and response than not displaying an image at all [27]. Moreover, despite an
26 aesthetically pleasant (and maybe, elaborated [79]) image may boost attention and enhance
27 intention to purchase, for products that are visually attractive enough it may be preferable to actually
28 show the product itself through a transparent window [18]. In addition, given that imagery is more
29 vivid and salient than texts, it may be a good idea to decide which kind of cue (imagery or text) is
30 more appropriate depending on the perceived valence of the attributes to be conveyed (i.e., whether
31 those attributes are regarded by consumers as positive or negative). If the product information to be
32 conveyed is perceived as positive, using images rather than texts may enhance consumer
33 expectations and response [22]. Conversely, relying on packaging imagery to communicate product
34 attributes that are not unequivocally positive, such as sweetness (which may be appealing from a
35 sensory point of view, but ambivalent about whether the product is healthy) may negatively affect
36 consumer attitude [23,80]. Furthermore, the inherently ambiguity of images should be kept in mind,
37 and caution should be taken to make sure that consumers infer the desired meaning in order to avoid
38 confusion [14,17]. Finally, although the effects of misleading packaging imagery remain to be
39 explored, it is reasonable to think that using misleading or dishonest imagery (e.g. pictures that
40 clearly exaggerate a product attribute) will negatively impact in consumer attitude towards the
41 product and intention to purchase [9,16].

1 **6. Conclusions**

2 The findings reported here have potential implications for both designers and policy makers alike,
3 since they pinpoint that the way in which consumers perceive and consume a product may be
4 modulated by manipulating the images depicted on its packaging. However, key issues such as the
5 effects of misleading images on consumer attitude towards the product, the emotional impact of
6 imagery, the potential role of instructed mental simulations in promoting optimal food choice, the
7 moderating role of individual differences, and the mechanisms underlying many of the discussed
8 effects are far from being clear. In addition, the application of recent developments such as virtual
9 reality or augmented reality technologies to the field of packaging imagery is still to be explored.
10 Despite the recent efforts made in this area, further research is needed to continue expanding our
11 knowledge on the effects, risks and opportunities of packaging imagery.

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- 1 **Declaration of interest**
- 2 None.

1 Selected references

2 *Of outstanding interest ***

- 3 • [4] An extensive and deep overview of the most recent advances in the field of packaging
4 design from a multisensory approach. In the context of this discussion, chapters 1, 3, 7, 8, 9
5 and 10 may be of special interest for the reader.
- 6 • [11] This paper provides an outstanding summary and a comprehensive review of the
7 semiotic theoretical framework applied to the case of packaging imagery.
- 8 • [39] In this paper, the authors demonstrate that depicting the food portion in a smaller
9 container makes consumers perceive it as being larger and, thereby, to increase purchase
10 intention, to evaluate it as being more appetizing, and to reduce the size of the portion they
11 serve themselves.

12 *Of special interest **

- 13 • [13] It studies how the individual effects of different packaging cues (namely, colours and
14 patterns) combine when both cues are presented together. It shows that when the
15 interpretation given to different package cues is not congruent, the effects of some design
16 cues dominate over the others.
- 17 • [14] A study investigating the mechanism by which ambiguous packaging images are
18 interpreted by assessing the effect of congruency between imagery meaning and product
19 category on classification easiness. In addition, they assess how the rhetorical style of the
20 image (i.e., whether its interpretation is literal or metaphorical) affects the cognitive effort
21 necessary to process it.
- 22 • [26] It assesses how the products shown accompanying the main product in a package
23 serving suggestion affect calorie estimation, and study different boundary conditions at play
24 in that process. Their findings indicate that depicting healthy products next to a healthy base
25 does not significantly impact calorie estimation, but that depicting healthy products next to
26 an unhealthy product makes consumers to underestimate the product calories.
- 27 • [28] A study showing how imagery can be used to convey information referred to a sensory
28 attribute of the product (in their case, coffee strength) both by depicting a metaphorical
29 subject (a lion) and by manipulating the image location (with the lower parts of the package
30 being associated with strong flavour).
- 31 • [44] The authors show that a semiotic analysis can confidently predict the associations that
32 consumers will infer from the package's graphic design, and that such associations are
33 stable across gender, generation, and product expertise.
- 34 • [69] Through seven studies, the authors show that unrealistic images (e.g., drawings
35 compared to photographs) attenuate consumers' judgments of the product's attributes
36 because they suppress the mental simulation of consumption and decrease confidence in
37 judgement. Accordingly, they propose that if the main characteristics of the depicted product
38 are perceived as drawbacks (benefits), that may lead to an increase (decrease) in
39 consumption.

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1 Tables and figures

Table 1

Studies investigating the effects of showing/manipulating different imagery features.

Note: Although some of these studies are not specifically focused on packaging imagery, we have considered them relevant for this discussion due to the high applicability of their findings to the field of packaging design.

Image subject	Food	Product	[12,20,21,22,33–37,39,67]
		Ingredients	[7,11,16,23,30–35,66,80,81]
		Garnish/ serving suggestion	[24–27]
		Inedible food ¹	[22,31,33]
		Non-food	Product-related
		Non-product-related	[6,14,17,28,50–53,78]
Image pictorial style ²			[11,66–70]
Image rhetorical style ³			[6,14,17,28,34,50,54,61,62]
Image size/ serving portion size			[12,38–41,77]
Image location			[28,54,56–60]
Image orientation/ viewing angle			[63–65]

¹ Images depicting raw or spoiled ingredients.

² Whether the image is a drawing or a photograph.

³ Images with metaphorical/ symbolical meanings.

2

3

4 **Fig. 1.** Depicting an angular fire icon on a bag of nuts (left) makes consumers interpret that the nuts
 5 are spicy, whereas a rounded fire icon (right) makes them rather interpret that the nuts have been
 6 roasted [17].

1

2

Fig. 2. Consumers expect the soft cheese depicted with a salad (left) to be saltier and healthier than the soft cheese depicted with some quince (right), thereby increasing willingness to buy [27].

3

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Fig. 3. Although both depictions of the pizza are the same size, the Delboeuf illusion makes the one in the left look 17% larger than the one in the right. Thus, the package in the left nudges consumers to serve themselves a smaller portion while increasing intention to purchase [39].

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7

- 1 **Declaration of interest**
- 2 None.

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